

Immunotoxicity of stainless-steel nanoparticles obtained after 3D printing

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to investigate the *in vitro* effects of nanoparticles (NPs) produced during the selective laser melting (SLM) of 316 L stainless steel metal powder on the immune response in a human blood model. Experimental data did not reveal effect on viability of 316 L NPs for the tested doses. Functional immune assays showed a significant immunosuppressive effect of NPs. There was moderate stimulation (117%) of monocyte phagocytic activity without significant changes in phagocytic activity and respiratory burst of granulocytes. A significant dose-dependent increase in the levels of the pro-inflammatory cytokine TNF- α was found in blood cultures treated with NPs. On the contrary, IL-8 chemokine levels were significantly suppressed. The levels of the pro-inflammatory cytokine IL-6 were reduced by only a single concentration of NPs. These new findings can minimise potential health risks and indicate the need for more research in this area.

1. Introduction

Currently, mankind is experiencing the fastest development of technology in its history (Chueh et al., 2020, Acharya et al., 2023). Efficient production of high-functionality devices is becoming the standard for today's industry. However, achieving the increasing demands is not always easy and requires collaboration across many different disciplines. Turning vision into reality starts with finding the right combination of materials to obtain the desired properties and continues with the development of a simple manufacturing process that allows the final product to be customized for the purpose (Lin et al., 2019, Jansa et al., 2023, Dvorsky et al., 2023, Wang et al., 2023). One such manufacturing process is additive manufacturing (AM), which is based on creating a three-dimensional object, layer by layer, based on digital data (Vaezi et al., 2013, Thurzo et al., 2022). AM uses different material input components and their combinations to create objects (Bandyopadhyay and Heer, 2018, Goh et al., 2019). ISO/ASTM 52 900

defines seven macro categories of printing techniques. These seven categories are differentiated depending on the production technology, the specific materials (polymers, metals, ceramics, composites, wax, paper, gypsum) and the final print characteristics. It includes vat photopolymerization, material extrusion, material jetting, binder jetting, powder bed fusion, direct energy deposition and sheet lamination (Andreacola et al., 2023).

A specific area of AM is the fabrication of objects from metal alloys, in particular selective laser melting (SLM) (Wu et al., 2022, Měsíček et al., 2022). The advantage of the SLM method is the total melting of the powder into a liquid state, thus achieving excellent homogeneity of the print. Furthermore, better mechanical properties, porosity reduction and increased control over the crystal structure of the resulting material are achieved (Cegan et al., 2020, Park et al., 2021, Nandhakumar and Venkatesan, 2023). SLM has the potential to completely replace conventional metal fabrication methods such as forging or casting (Calignano et al., 2017, Harun et al., 2018). Currently, the SLM method has

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already replaced some manufacturing processes in the medical (Podgórski et al., 2023, Zhang and Guan, 2023), automotive and aerospace industries (Gisario et al., 2019).

Recent studies have mainly focused on the optimization of AM methods, describing possible applications or the potential environmental impact. In particular, the dependence of the final print properties on the optimization of the printing process has been a major topic (Ruberu et al., 2021, Praneeth et al., 2023, Feng et al., 2023, Man et al., 2023). The influence of process parameters on the properties of printed components is well known. This is one of the most important aspects in

the study of AM, especially metallic materials. Different printing parameters affect the final printout. Research studies (Andreacola et al., 2021, Andreacola et al., 2023, Brando et al., 2023) have focused on evaluating the effect of different printing process parameters on the mechanical and microstructural behavior of 3D printed steels as well as on the dynamic effects of the printout. For example, (Andreacola et al., 2021, Andreacola et al., 2023, Brando et al., 2023) studied the effect of several specific printing parameters on the mechanical properties of 17-4PH stainless steel, which is one of the most widely used metals for selective laser melting (SLM) technology. They assessed the effect of

Fig. 1. Particle morphology. (A) SEM image of primary 316 L stainless steel powder. Size fractions 15–45 μm. Sieved, re-used 5 times. (B) SEM image of the powder mixture obtained after the 3D printing process from the Renishaw AM400 chamber. (C) SEM/STEM image of the nanoparticles used for the analyses.

different printing directions and sample inclinations on the mechanical behavior of the material along with the consequences of heat treatment (Andreacola et al., 2021, Andreacola et al., 2023, Brando et al., 2023). There is not a lot of research dealing with the potential health risks these manufacturing processes bring. These are mainly the risks associated with occupational exposure to particles of sizes up to nanoscale that are released during AM, air contamination by these particles and possible other risks depending on the use of the print (Pernetti et al., 2023). Examples include medical applications where, in the form of implants, abrasion of the material in the human body may occur, resulting in the release of metal particles and ions from the surface of the print into the surrounding tissue.

Metal particles and ions may interact with the organism. To understand this interaction, it is necessary to observe both sides of the interaction: what happens to the particles and what happens to the organism (Filipová et al., 2012). Usually, the particles are recognized as foreign substances in the organism. Thus, they can be bound to antigens and recognized by receptors on the surface of phagocytes, and subsequently phagocytosed. However, this is only of importance before the inflammatory response begins, during the inflammatory response, secreted molecular markers can already react with the particles and modify the immune response (Filipová 2022). Depending on the size and assumption that the metal particles are small enough, these particles can penetrate the cells where they can directly interact with DNA molecules, which can lead to genotoxicity (Linhart, 2022, Xiao et al., 2021).

This study examines the immune cell response and inflammatory response to 316 L stainless steel metal NPs formed as a by-product of AM. The NPs are formed under reduced inert gas buoyancy directly above the laser melt bath. The formation of the spherical particles, the method of collection and their detailed characterization have been done previously (Dvorsky et al., 2023). Immune assays evaluating lymphocyte function, phagocytic activity, respiratory burst of leukocytes and *in vitro* cytokine production were performed on human blood to determine the potential immunotoxicity of the NPs.

This research aims to contribute to filling the gaps in current research, verify the environmental safety of AM processes and demonstrate the potential impacts of degradation of 316 L austenitic alloy prints in medical applications.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Preparation of NPs

The studied mixture of particles of different sizes was formed by SLM from a primary powder of 316 L metal alloy (Renishaw), size fraction 15–45 μm (Fig. 1 (A)), during the process of Renishaw AM400. Printing process parameters were power size = 200 W, laser spot size = 70 μm , scanning speed = 650 mm/s, hatch distance = 0.110 mm, scanning pattern = stripes, platform temperature = without pre-heat, building chamber ~ 60 °C. The powder material was collected from the printing chamber after the build, from the chamber walls (Fig. 1 (B)). The collected condensate mixture was subjected to particle size separation, to separate the primary particles, from the rest of the fine fraction (Dvorsky et al., 2023). In this way, a nanopowder was obtained (Fig. 1 (C)) usable for subsequent analyses, in collaboration with the research team of Prof. Dvorský, VSB-TUO and colleagues from Protolab, VSB-TUO.

2.2. Characterization of 316 L NPs

The morphology of 316 L NPs was characterized by scanning electron microscopy (SEM, ThermoFisher Scientific, USA) and scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM, JOEL, USA). The size distribution of the NPs was determined using the dynamic Z-potential light scattering method (Malvern, UK).

2.3. Samples preparation for characterization

316 L NPs were dispersed in two media: RPMI 1640 cell culture medium (Sigma Aldrich) without serum (RPMI BSM) and complete RPMI containing 10% fetal calf serum (FCS) (Sigma Aldrich) (RPMI SM) in 5 concentrations (75 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$, 15 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$, 3 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$, 0.6 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$, 0.12 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$) followed by sonication (Ultrasonic Cleaner USC - T, frequency 45 kHz, VWR, CZ) for 20 min at room temperature. Concentrations 75 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$, 15 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$, 3 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$, 0.6 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$, 0.12 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ correspond to the concentrations: 106 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, 21 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ 4 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ 0.85 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ and 0.17 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ in the traditional expression.

2.4. Preparation of 316 L NPs dispersion for *in vitro* studies

316 L NPs were dispersed in RPMI 1640 BSM to prepare a stock solution (75 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$, i.e., 106 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) followed by sonication (Ultrasonic Cleaner USC - T, frequency 45 kHz, VWR, CZ) for 20 min, room temperature. The dispersion was diluted with the RPMI BSM to prepare a series of particle concentrations (0.12, 0.6, 3, 15, and 75 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$, i.e., 0.17, 0.85, 4.24, 21.21, and 106 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$). Before each experiment, fresh dispersions were prepared. Dispersions were vortexed (BioTech, CZ) and immediately added to the heparin blood.

2.5. Collection of blood

Peripheral venous blood was collected from fasted adult volunteers into vacuum collection tubes containing heparin. Each had 20 mL of blood drawn by a licensed staff member. Volunteers felt healthy and were asked about the presence of known immune disease and acute infection by a doctor. Each subject signed a written consent form and was given information regarding blood donation for research purposes (SZU 11/2022).

2.6. Assessment of Endotoxin Contamination

Endotoxin contamination of 316 L NPs was assessed with a commercial End-point chromogenic Limulus Amoebocyte Lysate (LAL) assay (BIOENDO) according to the manufacturer's instructions. Samples of NPs of three concentrations (75, 3, 0.12 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$) were tested. No endotoxin was detected in any of the samples. The assay sensitivity was 0.01 EU/mL.

2.7. Viability and mitogen-stimulated lymphocyte proliferation (LTT)

Viability of 316 L NPs was determined as proliferative activity of unstimulated blood cells by incorporating [^3H]-thymidine into nuclear DNA. LTT was used to quantify the proliferative response of human blood cells due to a selected mitogenic stimulus. Proliferating cells synthesize DNA using four purine nucleotides. One of these nucleotides was radiolabeled with [^3H]-thymidine and the degree of proliferation was examined by determining the incorporation of radioactivity into DNA using a Microbeta 2 liquid scintillation counter (PerkinElmer). Human heparinized whole blood (150 μL) diluted 1:15 in complete RPMI 1640 medium containing 10% FCS, L-glutamine, and gentamycin (Sandoz) was dispensed in triplicates in wells of a 96-well microtiter culture plate under sterile conditions. Phytohemagglutinin (PHA; 25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, Sigma Aldrich) and pokeweed mitogen (PWM; 2.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, Sigma Aldrich) were added in a volume of 25 μL to the cultures. Cultures were cultivated at 37 °C in 5% CO_2 atmosphere. After 24 h, 316 L NPs in 5 concentrations (0.12, 0.6, 3, 15, and 75 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$) in volume of 25 μL were added to the cultures. Doxorubicin (0.1 mg/mL, Medac) was used as a cytotoxic suppressive control. Then the plates were incubated for an additional 48 h of the whole 72 h incubation period. Twenty-four hours before the end of cultivation, cultures were pulsed with 1 μCi [^3H]-thymidine (Perkin Elmer) diluted in a medium (20 μL). After the 72 h incubation, cell cultures were harvested onto the glass filter paper

(Perkin Elmer), which was placed into a scintillation fluid (Perkin Elmer), and radioactivity was measured as counts per minute (cpm)/per culture in triplicates for each variable. Interference of the particles with the assay was tested by measuring cpm in cultures with the corresponding NP concentrations (0.12–75 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$) added into the wells at the end of experiments five minutes before cell harvesting.

2.8. Phagocytic activity and respiratory burst of leukocytes

Phagocytic activity of two cell types: monocytes and granulocytes and respiratory burst of granulocytes was examined by a Cytomics FC 500 flow cytometer (Beckman Coulter). One hundred fifty μL of human heparinized blood (diluted 1:1 in RPMI-1640 consisting of 10% FCS, L-glutamine, and gentamycin) was distributed into wells of 96-well culture microplate under a sterile condition. Twenty-five microliters of NPs 316 L (0.12–75 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$) were added, and the mixture was incubated for 24 h. After the incubation, blood (30 μL) from each well was pipetted into the tube and hydroethidine solution (10 μL , Polysciences) was added. First, the samples were incubated at 37 °C for 15 min and 3 μL of fluorescein-labelled *Staphylococcus aureus* bacteria (1.4×10^6 per test, Molecular Probes) was added. Second, all tubes were incubated at 37 °C for another 15 min, the samples were put on ice, and cold lysis solution (700 μL , Beckman Coulter) was added. In the control tubes, *S. aureus* was added after the lysis solution. The results were analyzed in duplicate by flow cytometry as follows: % of phagocytic granulocytes = phagocytic granulocytes / all granulocytes. Interference of 316 L NPs with the assay was tested by measuring the same control tubes without 316 L and 2 minutes after the addition of 316 L NPs.

2.9. In vitro production of cytokines in cell culture supernatants

Human heparinized blood was diluted in complete RPMI 1640 (10% FCS) medium, PHA (25 mg/mL) was added, and the mixture was incubated at 37 °C for 72 h. The NP dispersion was added 24 h after the beginning of the 72 h incubation period. Supernatants from cell cultures were isolated and frozen at –70 °C. Concentrations of IL-6, IL-8, and TNF- α in cell supernatants were analyzed by ELISA kits according to the procedure recommended by the manufacturer (TNF- α , IL-6 – AbCam, IL-8 – FineTest).

2.10. Statistical analysis

SPSS software was used for statistical analysis. Data are presented as the mean standard error of the mean (SEM). Multiple measurements from each individual were averaged and used as a single value for analysis. The Shapiro–Wilk test was applied to test the normality of the data distribution. A Student t-test (for normally distributed data sets) or Mann–Whitney tests (for non-normally distributed datasets) were used to determine differences between exposed and control groups. Differences with $p < 0.05$ were considered statistically significant. P values are given as follows: * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$.

3. Results and discussion

3D printing is an innovative technology with a wide range of promising industrial and medical applications. The creation of materials during 3D printing can lead to the release of particles of sizes up to nanoscale as by-products. Preliminary evaluation of the potential exposure during laser metal deposition showed a high release of NPs from the powder head on the device (average 138,713 n/cm^3 during printing, with maximum values exceeding 10^6 n/cm^3) (Pernetti et al., 2023). Due to their size, NPs may persist for a long time in the respirable form, with a high probability of occupational inhalation exposure. After inhalation, thanks to their small size, they may penetrate the lower respiratory tract and through the alveolar membrane of the lung alveoli into the human blood. A similar transition and subsequent systemic

exposure have been demonstrated for several metal NPs (Bocca et al., 2023a, 2023b, Cai et al., 2019, Tsuda et al., 2019, Hadrup et al., 2020), but little is known about the response of immune cells to these materials (Vallabani et al., 2022). Moreover, medical applications of long-term implants can result in the release of metal NPs from the surface of the print into the surrounding tissue and direct encounter of NPs with immune cells (Avery et al., 2023). This study aimed to evaluate the inflammatory response and immune cell response to stainless-steel NPs obtained after 3D printing.

3.1. Characterization of 316 L NPs

The size distribution of the 316 L NPs themselves for each analysis was below 100 nm, most commonly around 60 nm/1 particle. For all immunoassays, 316 L NPs were dispersed in two media (RPMI BSM and RPMI SM). For this reason, the size distribution of NPs was also determined in combination with these media, at 37 °C. The evaluation of the particle size distribution at time t_0 was identical to the result of the size distribution of the NPs alone. However, at time t_1 there was a slight aggregation of individual NPs into larger clusters (Fig. 2). The dominance of NP aggregates in the size range of 100–1000 nm was confirmed.

For the immunotoxicity assays, the NPs were always vortexed in the media, just before their use, to prevent their possible aggregation, which could be in the range of 100 nm to 1 μm at time t_1 .

3.2. Immunotoxicity tests of 316 L NPs

3.2.1. Viability of 316 L NPs in human peripheral blood cells

Cytotoxicity/viability of bulk medical grade 316 L stainless steel was widely tested (Senocak et al., 2021, Tapsir et al., 2018, Malheiro et al., 2011) meanwhile the effect of steel NPs on cytotoxicity/viability was less investigated (Almutairi et al., 2021) and data on 316 L NPs from the 3D printers are rare (Wang et al., 2022). In our study, no significant effect on the viability of human peripheral blood cells was found when measured as basal proliferative activity by incorporating radioactive thymidine using selected concentrations of 0.12 – 75 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ (Fig. 3). Our data support the findings of Vallabani et al. (Vallabani et al., 2022) that 316 L stainless steel suggests relatively low acute toxicity of condensates/spatter particles formed during selective laser melting printing using 316 L as original metal powders following exposure of human bronchial epithelial cells (HBEC) or monocytes/macrophages (THP-1). *In vitro* study on stainless steel NPs observed dose- and time-dependent cytotoxicity and apoptosis on hepatocyte-derived carcinoma (HuH-7 and CHANG) cells (Almutairi et al., 2021). NPs inhibited cell growth, GSH, and increased generation of intracellular ROS and SOD levels at higher concentrations administered. A key apoptotic mechanism of action of stainless-steel NPs in liver cells *via* activating the caspase-3 activity was identified (Almutairi et al., 2021). However, cytotoxicity is only one of the possible effects of NP action. One of the other possibilities is the modulation of the immune response.

3.2.2. The effect of 316 L NPs on proliferative function of lymphocytes

Lymphocytes are key cells of immune response playing an important role in possible nano-immune interactions. In our study, a significant dose-dependent immunosuppressive effect of NPs on the proliferative function of T-lymphocytes stimulated with PHA was found in peripheral blood. Middle and high doses of 316 L NPs (3–75 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$) reduced lymphocyte proliferation stimulated with phytohemagglutinin to 93–70% of values found in control cells (Fig. 4A). Moreover, decreased function of T-dependent B-cell response in cultures stimulated with pokeweed mitogen was found (Fig. 4B). Similar suppression in cell proliferation found in our study was observed in CEM cells (human acute lymphoblastic leukemia) exposed to bulk stainless steel 316 L (Zhang et al., 2009). On the other hand, no significant effect of stainless steel 316 L particles with size < 20 μm on T-lymphocyte activation quantified

Fig. 2. (A) Primary statistical size distribution of 316 L nanoparticles dispersed in RPMI BSM medium. (B) Primary statistical size distribution of 316 L nanoparticles dispersed in RPMI SM medium. (C) STEM image of 316 L nanoparticles in RPMI SM medium.

Fig. 3. **Viability of 316 L nanoparticles.** Viability was measured as basal proliferative activity of unstimulated human peripheral blood cells *in vitro* exposed to 316 L nanoparticles for 48 h exposure. The incorporation of [^3H]-thymidine into replicating cells was determined. Ctr – control group ($n = 7$). Blood was exposed to 5 different concentrations of nanoparticles: 0.12 – 75 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$. Results are expressed as cpm (counts per minute)/ per culture. Bars indicate mean group values (mean + SEM).

by *in vitro* production of cytokines by peripheral blood mononuclear cells was found by Cachinho et al. (Cachinho et al., 2013). Similar findings were published by Stio et al. (Stio et al., 2016) and Talha et al. (Talha et al., 2014) who reported that the steel bulk samples were ineffective in influencing peripheral blood mononuclear cell proliferation (Stio et al., 2016) or cell proliferation of Dalton's lymphoma cell line (Talha et al., 2014). Inconsistency in findings is supplemented by results of Avery et al. who found high recruitment of CD4 $^+$ T-cells, neutrophils and pro-inflammatory macrophages in mice implanted with stainless steel implants (Avery et al., 2023). Associated *in vitro* experiments in bone marrow-derived mouse macrophages co-cultured on stainless steel implants showed increased polarization of T-cells towards Th1/Th17 subsets and decreased Th2/Treg polarization compared to Ti substrates (Avery et al., 2023).

3.2.3. The effect of 316 L NPs on phagocytic activity and respiratory burst of peripheral blood leukocytes

One of the first cells involved in organism host resistance against invasion of particles of different origins to blood is the phagocytic system. Possible interactions of 316 L NPs with professional phagocytic

Fig. 4. A-B. Proliferative activity of blood lymphocytes. The proliferative activity of lymphocytes in response to mitogens (A) phytohaemagglutinin and (B) pokeweed mitogen in the human peripheral blood *in vitro* exposed to 316 L nanoparticles (NPs) for 48 h was measured as the incorporation of [³H]-thymidine into replicating cells. Ctr – control group (n = 8). Blood was exposed to 5 different concentrations of nanoparticles: 0.12 – 75 µg/cm². Results are expressed as cpm (counts per minute)/ per culture. Data are depicted using violin plots. The blue whiskers show 95% confidence interval. The shape of the violin displays a distribution of values. Significance: *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001.

cells were assessed during cultivation with the human peripheral blood of 8 volunteers. The cell exposure to 316 L NPs did not affect the ability of granulocytes to phagocyte *Staphylococcus aureus* (Fig. 5A). Function of respiratory burst was also resistant toward the presence of NPs in blood cultures (Fig. 5B). Similarly, no significant alterations in phagocytic activity of monocytes were found in cells *in vitro* exposed to 316 L NPs (Fig. 5C) however slight increase (117%) in phagocytic activity of cells administered with low doses might indicate an intensified effort of cells to get rid of all kinds of particles. The phenomenon that the uptake of non-stimulatory cargo-free particles enhances the phagocytic ability of monocytes, macrophages and neutrophils is described by Sharma et al. (Sharma et al., 2022). The enhancement in phagocytic ability was independent of particle properties, such as size or the base material constituting the particle. Administered in mice as a prophylactic, particulates enable faster clearance of *E. coli* and *Staphylococcus epidermidis* (Sharma et al., 2022).

Similarly, to our 316 L NPs, the phagocytic activity of monocytes was stimulated after exposure to magnetic NPs (Donini et al., 2023), titanium dioxide NPs (Pinsino et al., 2015), polysaccharides encapsulated into PLGA NPs (Wusiman et al., 2019) or formulation of ZnO NPs and

Fig. 5. A-C. Phagocytic activity and respiratory burst of leukocytes. Phagocytic activity of granulocytes and monocytes in the human peripheral blood *in vitro* exposed to 316 L nanoparticles for 48 h was evaluated using ingestion of fluorescein-labeled *Staphylococcus aureus*, and the respiratory burst was monitored using hydroethidine by flow cytometry. Ctr - control group (n = 8). Blood was exposed to 5 different concentrations of nanoparticles: 0.12 – 75 µg/cm². Results are expressed as the percentage of phagocytic activity and respiratory burst. Bars indicate the mean group activity of blood cells (mean + SEM).

cottonseed oil with α -tocopherol (Sobrevilla-Hernández et al., 2023). The stimulatory effect of NPs on neutrophils was found in the case of titanium dioxide, zinc oxide and cerium dioxide NPs (Babin et al., 2015). Phagocytic activity as the old mechanism of host defense is relatively resistant to xenobiotics, however, some NPs such as stainless-steel welding fume or Ni-Cu welding fume particles, carboxyl polystyrene or CuO NPs can weaken this barrier (Antonini et al., 2007, Badding et al., 2014, Prietl et al., 2014, Tulińska et al., 2022).

3.2.4. The effect of 316 L NPs on production of cytokines

The *in vitro* production of cytokines evaluates the complex functions of immune cells present in the blood. Levels of proinflammatory cytokines TNF- α , IL-6 and chemokine IL-8 measured in human blood cell culture supernatants are shown in Fig. 6A-C. A significant dose-dependent increase in proinflammatory cytokine TNF- α was found in peripheral blood cultures treated with high doses of 316 L NPs (15–75 µg/cm²). TNF- α is primarily produced by macrophages, but it is produced also by other cells including lymphoid cells. The level of proinflammatory cytokine IL-6 secreted also by macrophages was significantly suppressed (89% of control) by a single concentration of 316 L NPs (3 µg/cm²); while IL-6 production in cultures exposed to any other dose of 316 L NPs was not altered (Fig. 6B). Administration of

Fig. 6. A-C. Concentrations of cytokines TNF-α and IL-6 and chemokine IL-8 in blood cell culture supernatants. Cytokines were measured in PHA phytohemagglutinin-stimulated blood cell culture supernatants using the ELISA method. Ctrl - control group (n = 8–9). Blood was exposed to 5 different concentrations of nanoparticles: 0.12 – 75 μg/cm². Results are expressed in pg/mL as mean group levels of cytokines (mean + SEM). TNF- tumor necrosis factor, IL - interleukin. Significance: * p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001.

316 L NPs to blood cells significantly suppressed levels of IL-8 in supernatants in all tested concentrations of NPs. Significantly reduced *in vitro* production of IL-8 chemoattractant for neutrophils produced primarily by monocytes was not reflected in the suppression of phagocytosis.

Similarly, to our findings of increased TNF-α, indicating a pro-inflammatory effect of 316 L NPs, flux-cored wires stainless-steel welding fume particles also induced *in vitro* release of inflammatory cytokines TNF-α and IL-8 in THP-1 cells (McCarrick et al., 2021).

Results of *in vivo* animal studies showed that the initial pro-inflammatory effects of particles found after short-term exposure can disappear with the establishment of homeostasis in long-term animal observations. This effect can be shown in the study of Singh et al. (Singh et al., 2018) who found that rabbits exposed to stainless steel wear particles have increased amounts of TNF-α and IL-6 in the rabbit tissue specimens at 12 weeks but there was a decrease for both at 24 weeks (Singh et al., 2018). Another study indicated a similar transitory effect of thermal spray coating aerosols generated from stainless-steel wire in rats exposed by inhalation. Animals had a significant change in proteins IL-18, MIP-1α, VEGF, LIX, fractalkine, IP-10, and EGF in bronchoalveolar lavage fluid 1 day after exposure. 7 days after thermal spray coating exposure, the cytokines/chemokines reached homeostasis and only MIP-1α and fractalkine, were altered (Kodali et al., 2022).

In fact, most studies concluded that stainless steel NPs of different

origins, sizes and shapes were not potent initiators of the inflammatory response. The closest similar particles were used in the study of Vallabani et al. (Vallabani et al., 2022) who found no effect of a mixture of condensate and laser spatter particles (collected after selective laser melting printing of different metal alloys powders) on cytokine/chemokine release (TNF-α, IL-6, IL-8, IL-1β, IL-18, IL-10 and MCP-1) in THP-1 macrophages.

In vivo inhalation study on related stainless-steel welding fume particles also did not show the effect on levels of TNF-α, in bronchoalveolar lavage in exposed rats (Antonini et al., 2007). A 28-day inhalation study in rats exposed to stain-less steel 316 L powder showed an accumulation of metal particles in the lung lobes, but no histopathological signs of inflammation were found (Stockmann-Juvala et al., 2013).

In our study, a significant suppressive effect of 316 L NPs on *in vitro* production of chemokine IL-8 was observed. Although NPs with anti-inflammatory effects aiming to suppress the production of IL-8 have been already synthesized (Abou Zaid et al., 2023, Zamansky et al., 2023, Xu et al., 2022, Li et al., 2022, Yusuf and Casey, 2019, Liao et al., 2018); in most published manuscripts, the effects of tested NPs on IL-8, TNF-α and IL-6 production were in similar line. Since in our study, simultaneously with the increased levels of cytokine TNF-α, the release of both IL-8 and IL-6 in 316 L NPs dosed cultures was suppressed, even in the case of IL-6 without a clear dose dependence; we hypothesize that the secretory function of macrophages (TNF-α, IL-6, IL-8) might be more sensitive to the effect of NPs than that of lymphocytes (TNF-α). In agreement with our findings, diverse effects on cytokine production in terms of stimulated secretion of inflammatory cytokines IL-1 and IL-6 and decreased secretion of IL-8 and IL-10 were reported by Soliman et al. in TiO₂ NPs orally administered rats (Soliman et al., 2013). In connection with the fact that IL-8 has been presented as one of the prominent promoters of tumor progression involved in cancer-related inflammation (Long et al., 2016), we suppose that a diverse effect on cytokine production might indicate the regulatory effort of the immune response to recover homeostasis. Further research will be needed to clarify this diverse effect.

4. Conclusions

Our research evaluated the potential immunotoxic impact of degradation of 316 L austenitic alloy prints in medical applications. A significant dose-dependent effect of 316 L NPs on adaptive immunity was manifested as a suppressed proliferative function of T-lymphocytes and T-dependent B-cells. A diverse effect on cytokine production in terms of increased TNF-α and decreased IL-8 and IL-6 might indicate the regulatory effort of the immune system to recover homeostasis. In conclusion, our study indicates possible immunomodulatory effects of 316 L NPs affecting innate and adaptive immune responses. This knowledge is important for human risk assessment and a new technological approach to the production of metal products using 3D technology. Further research in this area will lead to more extensive testing of the effect of NPs on cytokine production, as well as studies of the potential impact of other metallic materials used for 3D printing.

Institutional Review Board Statement

The study was conducted according to the guidelines of the Declaration of Helsinki and approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee of Slovak Medical University, Bratislava (protocol code SZU 11/2022).

Informed Consent Statement

Informed consent was obtained from all subjects involved in the study.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Lukán Norbert: Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Tulinská Jana:** Data curation, Methodology, Supervision, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Rollerová Eva:** Formal analysis, Writing – review & editing. **Dvorský Richard:** Formal analysis, Methodology, Validation. **Olšovská Eva:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Kukutschová Jana:** Funding acquisition, Methodology, Resources, Supervision, Validation. **Lehotská Mikušová Miroslava:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Gabor Roman:** Formal analysis. **Hajnýš Jíří:** Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **Szabová Michaela:** Formal analysis, Writing – review & editing. **Svoboda Ladislav:** Formal analysis. **Lísková Aurélie:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Methodology, Validation, Writing – original draft. **Horváthová Mira:** Formal analysis, Writing – review & editing. **Vilamová Zuzana:** Formal analysis, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data Availability

Data will be made available on request.

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References

- Abou Zaid, E.S., Mansour, S.Z., El-sonbaty, S.M., Moawed, F.S., Kandil, E.I., Haroun, R. A.-H., 2023. Boswellic acid coated zinc nanoparticles attenuate NF- κ B-mediated inflammation in DSS-induced ulcerative colitis in rats. *Int. J. Immunopathol. Pharmacol.* 37, 039463202211507 <https://doi.org/10.1177/03946320221150720>.
- Acharya, A., Chodankar, R.N., Patil, R., Patil, A.G., 2023. Assessment of knowledge, awareness, and practices toward the use of 3D printing in dentistry among dental practitioners and dental technicians: a cross-sectional study. *J. Oral. Biol. Craniofac. Res.* 13 (2), 253–258. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobcr.2023.02.001>.
- Almutairi, B., Ali, D., Yaseen, K.N., Alothman, N.S., Alyami, N., Almkhlaifi, H., Alakhtani, S., Alarifi, S., 2021. Mechanisms of apoptotic cell death by stainless steel nanoparticle through reactive oxygen species and caspase-3 activities on human liver cells. *Front. Mol. Biosci.* 8 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmolb.2021.729590>.
- Andreacola, F.R., Capasso, I., Langella, A., Brando, G., 2023. 3D-printed metals: process parameters effects on mechanical properties of 17–4 PH stainless steel. *Heliyon* 9 (7), e17698. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e17698>.
- Andreacola, F.R., Capasso, I., Pilotti, L., Brando, G., 2021. Influence of 3d-printing parameters on the mechanical properties of 17-4PH stainless steel produced through Selective Laser Melting. *Frat. Ed. Integrità Strutt.* 15 (58), 282–295. <https://doi.org/10.3221/IGF-ESIS.58.21>.
- Antonini, J.M., Stone, S., Roberts, J.R., Chen, B., Schwegler-Berry, D., Afshari, A.A., Frazer, D.G., 2007. Effect of short-term stainless steel welding fume inhalation exposure on lung inflammation, injury, and defense responses in rats. *Toxicol. Appl. Pharmacol.* 223 (3), 234–245. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.taap.2007.06.020>.
- Avery, D., Morandini, L., Celt, N., Bergey, L., Simmons, J., Martin, R.K., Donahue, H.J., Olivares-Navarrete, R., 2023. Immune cell response to orthopedic and craniofacial biomaterials depends on biomaterial composition. *Acta Biomater.* 161, 285–297. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actbio.2023.03.007>.
- Babin, K., Goncalves, D.M., Girard, D., 2015. Nanoparticles enhance the ability of human neutrophils to exert phagocytosis by a Syk-dependent mechanism. *Biochim. Et*

- Biophys. Acta (BBA) - Gen. Subj.* 1850 (11), 2276–2282. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbagen.2015.08.006>.
- Badding, M.A., Fix, N.R., Antonini, J.M., Leonard, S.S., 2014. A comparison of cytotoxicity and oxidative stress from welding fumes generated with a new nickel-, copper-based consumable versus mild and stainless steel-based welding in RAW 264.7 mouse macrophages. *PLoS One* 9 (6), e101310. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0101310>.
- Bandyopadhyay, A., Heer, B., 2018. Additive manufacturing of multi-material structures. *Mater. Sci. Eng.: R: Rep.* 129, 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mser.2018.04.001>.
- Bocca, B., Battistini, B., Leso, V., Fontana, L., Caimi, S., Fedele, M., Iavicoli, I., 2023a. Occupational exposure to metal engineered nanoparticles: a human biomonitoring pilot study involving Italian nanomaterial workers. *Toxicol. Ind. Health* 39 (2), 120. <https://doi.org/10.3390/toxics11020120>.
- Bocca, B., Leso, V., Battistini, B., Caimi, S., Senofonte, M., Fedele, M., Cavallo, D.M., Cattaneo, A., Lovreglio, P., Iavicoli, I., 2023b. Human biomonitoring and personal air monitoring. An integrated approach to assess exposure of stainless-steel welders to metal-oxide nanoparticles. *Environ. Res.* 216, 114736. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2022.114736>.
- Cachinho, S.C.P., Pu, F., Hunt, J.A., 2013. Cytokine secretion from human peripheral blood mononuclear cells cultured *in vitro* with metal particles. *J. Biomed. Mater. Res. Part A* 101A (4), 1201–1209. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jbm.a.34410>.
- Brando, G., Romana Andreacola, F., Capasso, I., Forni, D., Cadoni, E., 2023. Strain-rate response of 3D printed 17-4PH stainless steel manufactured via selective laser melting. *Constr. Build. Mater.* 409, 133971. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2023.133971>.
- Cai, J., Zang, X., Wu, Z., Liu, J., Wang, D., 2019. Translocation of transition metal oxide nanoparticles to breast milk and offspring: the necessity of bridging mother-offspring integration toxicological assessments. *Environ. Int.* 133, 105153. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2019.105153>.
- Calignano, F., Manfredi, D., Ambrosio, E.P., Biamino, S., Lombardi, M., Atzeni, E., Salmi, A., Minetola, P., Iuliano, L., Fino, P., 2017. Overview on additive manufacturing technologies. *Proc. IEEE* 105 (4), 593–612. <https://doi.org/10.1109/JPROC.2016.2625098>.
- Cegan, T., Pagac, M., Jurica, J., Skotnicova, K., Hajnýš, J., Horsak, L., Soucek, K., Krpec, P., 2020. Effect of hot isostatic pressing on porosity and mechanical properties of 316 L stainless steel prepared by the selective laser melting method. *Materials* 13 (19), 4377. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma13194377>.
- Chueh, Y.-H., Wei, C., Zhang, X., Li, L., 2020. Integrated laser-based powder bed fusion and fused filament fabrication for three-dimensional printing of hybrid metal/polymer objects. *Addit. Manuf.* 31, 100928. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.addma.2019.100928>.
- Donini, M., Pettinella, F., Zanella, G., Gaglio, S.C., Laudanna, C., Jimenez-Carretero, M., Jimenez-Lopez, C., Perduca, M., Dusi, S., 2023. Effects of magnetic nanoparticles on the functional activity of human monocytes and dendritic cells. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 24 (2), 1358. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms24021358>.
- Dvorský, R., Kukutschová, J., Pagáč, M., Svoboda, L., Šimonová, Z., Peterek Dědková, K., Bednář, J., Mendes, R.G., Matýšek, D., Malina, O., Tuček, J., Vilamová, Z., Kiselev, S., Gemming, T., Filip, P., 2023. Analysis and modelling of single domain core-shell (αFeNi/chromite) nanoparticles emitted during selective laser melting, and their magnetic remanence. *J. Clean. Prod.* 400, 136688. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.136688>.
- Feng, Y., Noda, M., Noguchi, Y., Matsushima, K., Yamada, T., 2023. Multi-material topology optimization for additive manufacturing considering dimensional constraints. *Comput. Methods Appl. Mech. Eng.* 410, 116027. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cma.2023.116027>.
- Filipová, Zuzana, Kukutschová, Jana, Maslák, Miroslav, 2012. *Rizika nanomateriálů, Vol. 1. Univerzita Palackého. ISBN 978-80-244-3201-4.*
- Gisario, A., Kazarian, M., Martina, F., Mehrpouya, M., 2019. Metal additive manufacturing in the commercial aviation industry: a review. *J. Manuf. Syst.* 53, 124–149. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmsy.2019.08.005>.
- Goh, G.D., Yap, Y.L., Agarwala, S., Yeong, W.Y., 2019. Recent progress in additive manufacturing of fiber reinforced polymer composite. *Adv. Mater. Technol.* 4 (1), 1800271. <https://doi.org/10.1002/admt.201800271>.
- Hadrup, N., Sharma, A.K., Loeschner, K., Jacobsen, N.R., 2020. Pulmonary toxicity of silver vapours, nanoparticles and fine dusts: a review. *Regul. Toxicol. Pharmacol.* 115, 104690. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yrtph.2020.104690>.
- Harun, W.S.W., Kamariah, M.S.I.N., Muhamad, N., Ghani, S.A.C., Ahmad, F., Mohamed, Z., 2018. A review of powder additive manufacturing processes for metallic biomaterials. *Powder Technol.* 327, 128–151. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2017.12.058>.
- Jansa, J., Volodarskaja, A., Hlinka, J., Zárybnická, L., Polzer, S., Kraus, M., Hajnýš, J., Schwarz, D., Pagáč, M., 2023. Corrosion and material properties of 316L stainless steel produced by material extrusion technology. *J. Manuf. Process.* 88, 232–245. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmapro.2023.01.035>.
- Kodali, V., Afshari, A., Meighan, T., McKinney, W., Mazumder, M.H.H., Majumder, N., Cumpston, J.L., Leonard, H.D., Cumpston, J.B., Friend, S., Leonard, S.S., Erdely, A., Zeidler-Erdely, P.C., Hussain, S., Lee, E.G., Antonini, J.M., 2022. In vivo and in vitro toxicity of a stainless-steel aerosol generated during thermal spray coating. *Arch. Toxicol.* 96 (12), 3201–3217. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00204-022-03362-7>.
- Liao, P.-C., Lai, M.-H., Hsu, K.-P., Kuo, Y.-H., Chen, J., Tsai, M.-C., Li, C.-X., Yin, X.-J., Jeyashoke, N., Chao, L.K.-P., 2018. Identification of β -Sisterosterol as in vitro anti-inflammatory constituent in *Moringa oleifera*. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 66 (41), 10748–10759. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jafc.8b04555>.
- Linhart, I., 2022. *Toxikologie: interakce škodlivých látek s živými organismy, jejich mechanismy, projevy a důsledky, Vol. 3. VŠCHT, ISBN 978-80-7592-103-1.*

- Lin, L., Kollipara, P.S., Zheng, Y., 2019. Digital manufacturing of advanced materials: Challenges and perspective. *Mater. Today* 28, 49–62. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matod.2019.05.022>.
- Li, Z., Tian, C., Jiao, D., Li, J., Li, Y., Zhou, X., Zhao, H., Zhao, Y., Han, X., 2022. Synergistic effects of silver nanoparticles and cisplatin in combating inflammation and hyperplasia of airway stents. *Bioact. Mater.* 9, 266–280. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bioactmat.2021.07.029>.
- Long, X., Ye, Y., Zhang, L., Liu, P., Yu, W., Wei, F., Ren, X., Yu, J., 2016. IL-8, a novel messenger to cross-link inflammation and tumor EMT via autocrine and paracrine pathways (Review). *Int. J. Oncol.* 48 (1), 5–12. <https://doi.org/10.3892/ijo.2015.3234>.
- Malheiro, V.N., Spear, R.L., Brooks, R.A., Markaki, A.E., 2011. Osteoblast and monocyte responses to 444 ferritic stainless steel intended for a magneto-mechanically actuated fibrous scaffold. *Biomaterials* 32 (29), 6883–6892. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biomaterials.2011.06.002>.
- Man, J., Blinn, B., Sulák, I., Kuběna, I., Smaga, M., Chlup, Z., Kruml, T., Beck, T., Polák, J., 2023. Formation of deformation induced martensite in fatigued 316L steels manufactured by selective laser melting (SLM). *Procedia Struct. Integr.* 43, 203–208. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prostr.2022.12.259>.
- McCarrick, S., Romanovski, V., Wei, Z., Westin, E.M., Persson, K.-A., Trydell, K., Wagner, R., Odneval, I., Hedberg, Y.S., Karlsson, H.L., 2021. Genotoxicity and inflammatory potential of stainless steel welding fume particles: an in vitro study on standard vs Cr(VI)-reduced flux-cored wires and the role of released metals. *Arch. Toxicol.* 95 (9), 2961–2975. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00204-021-03116-x>.
- Měsíček, J., Čegan, T., Ma, Q.-P., Halama, R., Skotnicová, K., Hajnýs, J., Juríca, J., Krpec, P., Pagač, M., 2022. Effect of artificial aging on the strength, hardness, and residual stress of SLM AISI10Mg parts prepared from the recycled powder. *Mater. Sci. Eng.: A* 855, 143900. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.msea.2022.143900>.
- Nandhakumar, R., Venkatesan, K., 2023. A process parameters review on selective laser melting-based additive manufacturing of single and multi-material: Microstructure, physical properties, tribological, and surface roughness. *Mater. Today Commun.* 35, 105538. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mtcomm.2023.105538>.
- Park, T.-H., Baek, M.-S., Hyer, H., Sohn, Y., Lee, K.-A., 2021. Effect of direct aging on the microstructure and tensile properties of AISI10Mg alloy manufactured by selective laser melting process. *Mater. Charact.* 176, 111113. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matchar.2021.111113>.
- Pernetti, R., Maffia, S., Previtali, B., Oddone, E., 2023. Assessment of nanoparticle emission in additive manufacturing: comparing wire and powder laser metal deposition processes. *J. Occup. Environ. Hyg.* 20 (8), 329–335. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15459624.2023.2208649>.
- Pinsino, A., Russo, R., Bonaventura, R., Brunelli, A., Marcomini, A., Matranga, V., 2015. Titanium dioxide nanoparticles stimulate sea urchin immune cell phagocytic activity involving TLR/p38 MAPK-mediated signalling pathway. *Sci. Rep.* 5 (1), 14492. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep14492>.
- Podgórski, R., Wojsiński, M., Trepkowska-Mejer, E., Ciach, T., 2023. A simple and fast method for screening production of polymer-ceramic filaments for bone implant printing using commercial fused deposition modelling 3D printers. *Biomater. Adv.* 146, 213317. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bioadv.2023.213317>.
- Praneeth, J., Venkatesh, S., Sivarama Krishna, L., 2023. Process parameters influence on mechanical properties of AISI10Mg by SLM. *Mater. Today: Proc.* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2022.12.222>.
- Prieti, B., Meindl, C., Roblegg, E., Pieber, T.R., Lanzer, G., Fröhlich, E., 2014. Nano-sized and micro-sized polystyrene particles affect phagocyte function. *Cell Biol. Toxicol.* 30 (1), 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10565-013-9265-y>.
- Ruberu, K., Senadeera, M., Rana, S., Gupta, S., Chung, J., Yue, Z., Venkatesh, S., Wallace, G., 2021. Coupling machine learning with 3D bioprinting to fast track optimisation of extrusion printing. *Appl. Mater. Today* 22, 100914. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apmt.2020.100914>.
- Senocak, T.C., Ezirmik, K.V., Aysin, F., Simsek Ozek, N., Cengiz, S., 2021. Niobium-oxynitride coatings for biomedical applications: its antibacterial effects and in-vitro cytotoxicity. *Mater. Sci. Eng.: C* 120, 111662. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.msec.2020.111662>.
- Sharma, P., Vijaykumar, A., Raghavan, J.V., Rananaware, S.R., Alakesh, A., Bodele, J., Rehman, J.U., Shukla, S., Wagde, V., Nadig, S., Chakrabarti, S., Visweswariah, S.S., Nandi, D., Gopal, B., Jhunjhunwala, S., 2022. Particle uptake driven phagocytosis in macrophages and neutrophils enhances bacterial clearance. *J. Control. Release* 343, 131–141. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jconrel.2022.01.030>.
- Singh, V., Rawlinson, J., Hallab, N., 2018. Stainless steel wear debris of a scoliotic growth guidance system has little local and systemic effect in an animal model. *J. Orthop. Res.* 36 (7), 1980–1990. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jor.23855>.
- Sobrevilla-Hernández, G., Franco-Molina, M.A., Zárate-Triviño, D.G., Kawas, J.R., Hernández-Martínez, S.P., García-Coronado, P.L., Santana-Krimskaya, S.E., Alvizco-Báez, C.A., Rodríguez-Padilla, C., 2023. Development of a new generation of miniemulsion based on cottonseed oil with α -tocopherol and ZnO and evaluation of its adjuvant activity. *PeerJ* 11, e14981. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.14981>.
- Soliman, M.M., Attia, H.F., Hussein, M.M., Mohamed, E.H., Ismail, T.A., 2013. Protective effect of n-acetylcysteine against titanium dioxide nanoparticles modulated immune responses in male albino rats. *Am. J. Immunol.* 9 (4), 148–158. <https://doi.org/10.3844/ajisp.2013.148.158>.
- Stio, M., Martinesi, M., Treves, C., Borgioli, F., 2016. Cultures and co-cultures of human blood mononuclear cells and endothelial cells for the biocompatibility assessment of surface modified AISI 316L austenitic stainless steel. *Mater. Sci. Eng.: C* 69, 1081–1091. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.msec.2016.08.010>.
- Stockmann-Juvala, H., Hedberg, Y., Dhinsa, N., Griffiths, D., Brooks, P., Zitting, A., Wallinder, I.O., Santonen, T., 2013. Inhalation toxicity of 316L stainless steel powder in relation to bioaccessibility. *Hum. Exp. Toxicol.* 32 (11), 1137–1154. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0960327112472354>.
- Talha, M., Kumar, S., Behera, C.K., Sinha, O.P., 2014. Effect of cold working on biocompatibility of Ni-free high nitrogen austenitic stainless steels using Dalton's Lymphoma cell line. *Mater. Sci. Eng.: C* 35, 77–84. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.msec.2013.10.017>.
- Tapsir, Z., Jamaludin, F.H., Pinguin-Murphy, B., Saidin, S., 2018. Immobilisation of hydroxyapatite-collagen on polydopamine grafted stainless steel 316L coating adhesion and in vitro cells evaluation. *J. Biomater. Appl.* 32 (7), 987–995. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0885328217744081>.
- Thurzo, A., Urbanová, W., Neuschlová, I., Paouris, D., Čverha, M., 2022. Use of optical scanning and 3D printing to fabricate customized appliances for patients with craniofacial disorders. *Semin. Orthod.* 28 (2), 92–99. <https://doi.org/10.1053/j.sodo.2022.10.005>.
- Tsuda, A., Donaghey, T.C., Konduru, N.V., Pyrgiotakis, G., Van Winkle, L.S., Zhang, Z., Edwards, P., Bustamante, J.-M., Brain, J.D., Demokritou, P., 2019. Age-dependent translocation of gold nanoparticles across the air–blood barrier. *ACS Nano* 13 (9), 10095–10102. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsnano.9b03019>.
- Tulinska, J., Mikusova, M.L., Liskova, A., Busova, M., Masanova, V., Uhnakova, I., Rollerova, E., Alacova, R., Krivosikova, Z., Wsolova, L., Dusinska, M., Horvathova, M., Szabova, M., Lukan, N., Stuchlikova, M., Kuba, D., Vecera, Z., Coufalik, P., Krumal, K., Mikuska, P., 2022. Copper oxide nanoparticles stimulate the immune response and decrease antioxidant defense in mice after six-week inhalation. *Front. Immunol.* 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fimmu.2022.874253>.
- Vaezi, M., Chianrabutra, S., Mellor, B., Yang, S., 2013. Multiple material additive manufacturing – Part 1: a review. *Virtual Phys. Prototyp.* 8 (1), 19–50. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17452759.2013.778175>.
- Vallabani, N.V.S., Alijagic, A., Persson, A., Odneval, I., Särndahl, E., Karlsson, H.L., 2022. Toxicity evaluation of particles formed during 3D-printing: cytotoxic, genotoxic, and inflammatory response in lung and macrophage models. *Toxicology* 467, 153100. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tox.2022.153100>.
- Wang, N., Meenashisundaram, G.K., Chang, S., Fuh, J.Y.H., Dheen, S.T., Senthil Kumar, A., 2022. A comparative investigation on the mechanical properties and cytotoxicity of cubic, octet, and TPMS gyroid structures fabricated by selective laser melting of stainless steel 316L. *J. Mech. Behav. Biomed. Mater.* 129, 105151. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmbbm.2022.105151>.
- Wang, W., Wei, J., Lei, D., Wang, S., Shang, S., Bai, B., Zhao, C., Zhang, W., Zhou, C., Zhou, H., Feng, S., 2023. 3D printing of lithium osteogenic bioactive composite scaffold for enhanced bone regeneration. *Compos. Part B: Eng.* 256, 110641. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2023.110641>.
- Wusiman, A., Xu, S., Ni, H., Gu, P., Liu, Z., Zhang, Y., Qiu, T., Hu, Y., Liu, J., Wu, Y., Wang, D., Lu, Y., 2019. Immunomodulatory effects of Alhagi honey polysaccharides encapsulated into PLGA nanoparticles. *Carbohydr. Polym.* 211, 217–226. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbpol.2019.01.102>.
- Wu, H., Liang, Z., Zhu, Z., Tang, B., Zhao, Q., 2022. Oxidation resistance of the 316L manufactured by cold-rolled and selective laser melting in CO2 and air. *Mater. Today Commun.* 33, 104889. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mtcomm.2022.104889>.
- Xiao, W., Wang, Y., Zhang, H., Liu, Y., Xie, R., He, X., Zhou, Y., Liang, L., Gao, H., 2021. The protein corona hampers the transcytosis of transferrin-modified nanoparticles through blood–brain barrier and attenuates their targeting ability to brain tumor. *Biomaterials* 274, 120888. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biomaterials.2021.120888>.
- Xu, X.Y., Moon, S.-K., Kim, J.-K., Kim, W.J., Kim, Y.-J., Kim, H., 2022. Structural properties and anti-dermatitis effects of flavonoids-loaded gold nanoparticles prepared by Eupatorium japonicum. *Front. Pharmacol.* 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2022.1055378>.
- Yusuf, A., Casey, A., 2019. Surface modification of silver nanoparticle (AgNP) by liposomal encapsulation mitigates AgNP-induced inflammation. *Toxicol. Vitro* 61, 104641. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tiv.2019.104641>.
- Zamansky, M., Zehavi, N., Sintov, A.C., Ben-Shabat, S., 2023. The fundamental role of lipids in polymeric nanoparticles: dermal delivery and anti-inflammatory activity of cannabidiol. *Molecules* 28 (4), 1774. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules28041774>.
- Zhang, Y.M., Chai, F., Hornez, J.-C., Li, C.L., Zhao, Y.M., Traisnel, M., Hildebrand, H.F., 2009. The corrosion and biological behaviour of titanium alloys in the presence of human lymphoid cells and MC3T3-E1 osteoblasts. *Biomed. Mater.* 4 (1), 015004. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-6041/4/1/015004>.
- Zhang, Q., Guan, Y., 2023. Application of metal additive manufacturing in oral dentistry. *Curr. Opin. Biomed. Eng.* 25, 100441. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cobme.2022.100441>.